

Table 2. Effects of elevated CO₂ level on the growth of rice at maturity and on the reproductive characteristics of rice.

Treatment	Culm length (cm)	Root dry weight (g/plant)	Shoot dry weight (g/Plant)	Root-shoot ratio	Grain yield (t/plant)	Panicles/plant (no.)	Filled grains/panicle (no.)	1,000 grain weight (g)
Ambient air	61.35 ± 0.9	1.63 ± 0.35	6.52 ± 0.92	0.25	6.35 ± 0.31	3.8 ± 0.2	52.7 ± 1.6	31.7 ± 0.8
Ambient plus 350 ppm CO ₂	68.4 ± 1.1	2.00 ± 0.24	6.47 ± 0.61	0.31	8.98 ± 0.41	3.9 ± 0.1	67.9 ± 1.4	33.9 ± 1.0
± (%)	+ 11.8	+ 23.0	- 0.7	+ 24	+ 41.4	+ 2.6	- 28.8	+ 6.9

plant culm length increased by 11.8%, root dry weight increased by 23%, and root-shoot ratio increased by 24%. Almost no change in shoot dry weight was observed (Table 2).

Grain yield per plant increased by 41.4% under elevated CO₂ levels. Increases in filled grains per panicle and 1,000-grain weight contributed to the higher yield. No significant change in panicles per plant occurred (Table 2).

Results of this study are similar to those of previous studies (Imai et al 1986,

Baker et al 1990, Ziska and Teramura 1992). Baker et al (1990), using IR30, observed that panicle number per plant was almost entirely responsible for differences in final grain yield among CO₂ treatments. Doubling the CO₂ concentration from 330 to 660 ppm resulted in a 32% increase in grain yield. Ziska and Teramura (1992) described differences in reproductive characteristics between IR36 and Fujiyama 5 cultivars. Considering the large diversity of growth and developmental properties in different

rice cultivars, more cultivars need to be studied under elevated CO₂.

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Modeling leaf and canopy photosynthesis of rice in response to carbon dioxide and temperature

K. J. Boote, N. B. Pickering, J. T. Baker, and L.H. Allen, Jr., University of Florida and United States Department of Agriculture, Agricultural Research Service (USDA-ARS), Gainesville, FL 32611, USA

Model equations were developed to predict leaf and canopy assimilation of rice as a function of CO₂, temperature, photosynthetic active radiation (PAR), time of day, leaf traits, and canopy leaf area index (LAI) as described by Boote and Pickering (1984). Predictions were compared with canopy assimilation measured on rice grown in sunlit, controlled-environment chambers under season-long treatments of CO₂ and temperature (Baker et al 1990, 1992). Apparent assimilation, CO₂, air temperature, and PAR were recorded at 5-min intervals throughout the day.

The model accounts for diffuse and direct beam interception of PAR, computes irradiance on sunlit and shaded leaf classes, and computes photosynthesis of sunlit and shaded leaf classes with asymptotic exponential equations (Boote and Pickering 1994). Temperature and CO₂ effects on quantum efficiency (QE)

1. Gross assimilation vs photosynthetic active radiation (PAR) at 160,330, and 660 vpm CO₂.

and light saturated leaf photosynthesis (P_{max}) are computed using equations 16.60 a, b of Farquhar and von Caemmerer (1982), assuming limiting RuBP and temperature effects on the specificity factor of rubisco for CO₂ vs O₂. The equations are scaled to a QE of 0.0541 mol/mol and a relative effect of 1.0 P_{max} at 30 °C and 350 vpm CO₂. Actual QE and P_{max} depend on intercellular CO₂ concentration (C_i), temperature, and oxygen.

2. Gross assimilation vs temperature at 350 or 700 vpm CO₂.

The canopy assimilation model was used with nonlinear regression to solve for single leaf P_{max} for individual rice canopies grown at a range of CO₂ levels and temperatures. For these regressions, we entered observed LAI, and 5-min averages of CO₂, air temperature, and PAR measured throughout the day for each chamber. Measured plants were 60 d old and LAI ranged from 5 to 11 in the two experiments. A spherical leaf angle distribution was assumed.

We hypothesized that there should be no trends in the solved values of Pmax for individual treatments, based on the assumption that our equations account for PAR and LAI effects, and that the QE and Pmax terms account for CO₂ and temperature effects. We then solved for one Pmax value to represent all CO₂ treatments, based on the same assumptions. Pmax thus reflects light-saturated rate at 350 vpm CO₂ and 30°C.

The trend for solved Pmax (of individual chambers) was to increase with increasing CO₂: 17.1, 16.3, 21.9, 29.3, 28.9, and 27.1 μmol CO₂/m² per s at 160, 250, 330, 500, 660, and 900 vpm CO₂, respectively. One solved Pmax (24.0) was adequate to predict canopy response at all CO₂ treatments, except at 160 and 250 vpm. The CO₂-related increase in Pmax and the fact that a single Pmax for all treatments was overpredicted at sub-ambient CO₂ indicated a problem with the assumption that the complete response to CO₂ can be modeled on the basis of energy limitation only.

Electro-transport rate in high light is reported to be inhibited as C_i falls below 300 vpm (Sharkey et al 1988). An asymptotic equation was added to rice Pmax as a function of C_i. This function describes CO₂ substrate limitations upon RuBP regeneration and upon rubisco activity. The 50% response of Pmax to C_i was achieved at 137 vpm CO₂. Figure 1 illustrates how well predicted canopy assimilation matched observed values for 160, 330, and 660 vpm CO₂ treatments using one value for Pmax (29.8 μmol CO₂/m² per s).

In the temperature experiment, rice canopies showed a trend for Pmax to increase from low to high temperature: 18.9, 24.1, 23.0, 24.7, and 39.6 μmol CO₂/m² per s at 25, 28, 31, 34, and 37°C growth/measurement temperature, respectively. Solving for a single Pmax (24.6) to represent all treatments overestimated assimilation at 25 °C and underestimated at higher temperatures.

Temperature effects on efficiency of electron use for CO₂ fixation are accounted for in QE and Pmax, but the equations had no temperature effect on electron transport capacity per se. Adding a linear temperature effect on Pmax

(electron transport) improved the fit considerably.

Linear regression was done for Pmax values vs temperature (10 values from two dates). The equation for temperature effect on Pmax was normalized to 1.0 at 30°C and had a base temperature of 6.4°C (relative = -0.272 + 0.0424°C). Model sensitivity analysis to temperature was then conducted at midday for Pmax = 24.0 μmol CO₂/m² per s, LAI = 5.0, and PAR = 1500 μmol/m² per s. Despite a linear increase in electron transport from 6° to 37°C, predicted canopy gross assimilation was within 98% of maximum from 24° to 32°C at 350 vpm CO₂, and from 28° to 40°C at 700 vpm CO₂ (Fig. 2).

The broad temperature optimum for canopy assimilation is consistent with our

measurements, meaning there were no major differences in canopy assimilation from 25° to 37°C.

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Carbon dioxide and nitrogen fertilizer effects on rice canopy carbon exchange, growth, and yield

J. T. Baker, L. H. Allen, Jr., K. J. Boote, and N. B. Pickering, University of Florida, Gainesville, and United States Department of Agriculture - Agricultural Research Service (USDA-ARS), USA

The current global rise in atmospheric CO₂ is now well-established and is largely attributed to the continuous burning of fossil fuels and large-scale deforestation. The Green Revolution in the tropics was made possible by the development of semidwarf, high-yielding cultivars that were fertilizer-responsive and resistant to lodging (Jennings et al 1979). Nitrogen fertilizer is an important limiting nutrient in the production of modern rice cultivars in Asia (De Datta 1981). The objectives of this study were to determine the effects and possible interactions of CO₂ and N fertilization on the growth, grain yield, and canopy gas exchange (photosynthesis, respiration and evapotranspiration) of rice.

Cultivar IR30 was grown under irrigated conditions in six sunlit controlled-environment plant growth chambers (aboveground dimensions 2 × 1 m cross section × 1.5 m high). Daytime CO₂ concentration was maintained at 330 (three chambers) and at 660 (three chambers) μmol CO₂/mol air. Rice was

direct seeded by hand into 11 rows in each chamber, 0.18 m apart, on 8 Jun 1990. Temperatures were controlled at 28/21/25 °C (daytime dry-bulb air temperature/ nighttime dry-bulb air temperature/flood water temperature). In each CO₂ treatment, N fertilizer (as urea) at 0, 100, or 200 kg/ha was applied to a loamy sand in three splits (1/2, 1/4, and 1/4) at 9, 35, and 59 after planting (DAP). Initial or pre-flood soil pH was 4.8; the NH₄-N 3.5 mg/kg; the NO₃-N, 0.5 mg/kg; and the organic matter content, 4.3%.

Nitrogen fertilization treatments did not significantly affect plant development rates in this experiment while CO₂ treatment effects on development were small. Logistic regression estimates of the day of 50% panicle appearance (near anthesis) indicated no N treatment effects on the number of days to anthesis while CO₂ enrichment tended to decrease the number of days to 50% panicle appearance by about 4-6 d.

Tillering, final biomass accumulation, and grain yield increased with both CO₂ enrichment and increasing N treatment. (See table for final grain yield, yield components, final aboveground biomass, and harvest index.)

As N treatment increased from 0 to 200 kg/ha, grain yields increased from 6.0 to 8.1 and 7.9 to 10.1 Mg/ha for the 330 and 660 mol/mol CO₂ treatments, respectively, because more grain-bearing